

**THE ROLE OF THE INTERFACE AND FIBER ANISOTROPY
ON CONTROLLING THE PERFORMANCE OF
POLYETHYLENE FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

The influence of the interface and fiber anisotropy on the performance of high-performance polyethylene (HP-PE)/epoxy composites was investigated. The relatively low experimentally found maximum values for shear- and transverse strength of HP-PE/ epoxy composites, incorporating surface treated fibers, are caused by a change in failure mode from debonding to fiber splitting with increasing levels of adhesion. To obtain more quantitative information about the role of fiber anisotropy on the strength of HP-PE composites, a finite element micromechanics analysis was utilized to predict ultimate composite properties. Theoretical values for transverse composite strength as obtained via micromechanics, assuming perfect adhesion, are in good agreement with experimental data for HP-PE composites incorporating surface treated fibers, indicating that the highly anisotropic character of HP-PE fibers plays a predominant role in the structural performance of composites based on these fibers.

KEYWORDS: Adhesion; Anisotropy; Failure mechanism; Fiber, polyethylene; Micromechanics; Strength; Shear; Transverse.

1. INTRODUCTION

High-performance polyethylene (HP-PE) fibers possess excellent mechanical properties in terms of high-specific strength and -stiffness [1] and are consequently an attractive candidate for composite applications. Moreover these fibers possess superior values for work to break in comparison with other reinforcing fibers. Despite these unique properties, main development areas in composite markets for the use of

these fibers are limited to reinforcements for impact or ballistic resistant composite structures. Little developments are considered with relation to structural applications due to poor compressive, shear and transverse properties of HP-PE composites.

It is generally recognised that the level of fiber/matrix adhesion is an essential factor for optimum translation of fiber properties to composite properties. From this point of view it is often assumed that the poor interfacial bond strength between the chemical inert and smooth HP-PE fibers and polymer matrices plays a predominant role in preventing the use of these fibers in structural applications [2]. Consequently, surface modifications of HP-PE fibers for improved adhesion to polymer matrices has been the subject of several studies [3-7]. A number of surface treatments have been proposed including acid etching, corona and plasma treatments. All treatments significantly improved the adhesion level, based on pull-out or interlaminar shear strength tests (ILSS), although plasma treatment was far more effective in raising the bond strength. Improved adhesion was attributed to surface pitting and consequently mechanical interlocking [3], increase in wettability [3,6] and the introduction of functional groups [5,7]. As tested by ILSS, composite shear strength could be increased to a value of approximately 31 MPa for plasma treated fibers [6]. The latter value seems to be the upper limit and inherently related to the one-dimensional character of HP-PE fibers.

Due to the highly anisotropic character of linear macromolecules, one focuses automatically on exploiting maximum strength/stiffness in one direction, i.e. fibers. However, in the case of fiber reinforced composites this anisotropic character can be a major disadvantage in e.g. off-axis (transverse/shear) or compressive loadings, especially when specific interactions between the molecules are absent like in the case of polyethylene. The stiffness matrix of a hypothetically perfect polyethylene crystal as calculated by Tashiro and Tadoro [8] shows that the modulus in the chain direction, reflected by the high C_{33} value, is orders of magnitude higher than the transverse or shear moduli of the crystal (see Figure 1).

$$C_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 7.99 & 3.28 & 1.13 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 3.28 & 9.92 & 2.14 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1.13 & 2.14 & \mathbf{316} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 3.19 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.62 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 3.62 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{GPa})$$

Figure 1. Theoretical moduli of polyethylene (single) crystal (after Tashiro & Tadoro).

To emphasise the importance of this highly anisotropic character of HP-PE fibers on composite strength, scanning electron micrograph (SEM) studies were performed on interlaminar fractured HP-PE/epoxy composites taken from Ref. [9], visualizing the change in failure mode after chromic acid surface treatment. Figure 2a shows a typical untreated HP-PE fiber revealing debonding after an ILSS test. Composites incorporating surface treated fibers showed a subsequent increase in ILSS from 14 to 29 MPa and fiber splitting (Figure 2b) indicating that composite properties are fiber dominated rather than interface dominated.

Figure 2a. Scanning electron micrograph of ILSS fracture surface of untreated HP-PE/epoxy composites showing debonding.

Figure 2b. Scanning electron micrograph of ILSS fracture surface of chromic acid treated HP-PE/epoxy composites showing fiber splitting.

The main objective of the present study was to investigate the role of fiber anisotropy on the performance of HP-PE composites. Preliminary results will be presented concerning the influence of this anisotropic character on the ultimate transverse tensile strength of HP-PE composites based on the properties of the constituents, i.e. fiber and matrix, using micromechanical analysis.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials Two types of material were used in this study. In view of experimental difficulties with respect to transverse fiber testing, ultradrawn ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMW-PE) tape, kindly provided by DSM Research, was used as an alternative for HP-PE fibers to investigate the transverse properties of oriented polyethylene structures. Unidirectional (UD) HP-PE/epoxy composites were prepared to study interfacial effects on composite properties.

2.1.1 *Ultradrawn UHMW-PE tapes* Apart from the production of fibers, based on the ultradrawability of solution-crystallized UHMW-PE (gelspinning) it is also possible to make other structures such as tapes [1]. Solution-crystallized UHMW-PE gels were prepared by continuously extruding a 15% solution of UHMW-PE (Himont HB 312, $M_w=1.5 \times 10^3$ kg/mol) in decalin. The solution was quenched in water and the resulting gel film was dried at ambient temperatures. The gel films were subsequently uniaxially stretched at a temperature of 110 °C to a drawratio of 20. Samples had a thickness of approximately 0.3 mm and a width of 30 mm. Test samples were cut from these tapes under an angle of 90° with the principal material direction, i.e. drawing direction.

2.1.2 *Composite laminates* In this study we used a HP-PE fiber (Spectra 1000) of Allied Signal. The matrix was an epoxy system of Shell (Epikote 828 EL/DX 6505/DX 690) based on bisphenol A and an anhydride curing agent. Plasma treated fibers were used to study the effect of improved adhesion on composite properties. UD-prepregs were manufactured on a drumwinder. After winding, the prepreg was B-staged in an oven and subsequently used to make UD-laminates which were cured for 5h under combined vacuum- and pressure conditions in a hot press at 80 °C. After curing samples were postcured for 12h at 110 °C. Transverse tensile specimens were cut from the laminate plates at an angles of 90° with the fiber direction using a diamond cutting wheel. Specimen dimensions were in accordance with ASTM D 3039 standard and were provided with adhesively bonded, tapered aluminum tabs.

2.2 Testing Transverse tensile tests for both ultradrawn UHMW-PE tapes and HP-PE fiber reinforced composites were performed on a Frank 81565 universal testing machine. Each specimen was loaded monotonically to fracture at a strain rate of 1 %/min. Fracture surfaces of the specimens were studied by SEM to illustrate differences in failure mode.

3. MICROMECHANICS

The results of the (transverse) tensile tests on the ultra-drawn UHMW-PE tapes, as a reference for transverse fiber properties, epoxy resin and HP-PE fiber reinforced composites are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1. *Transverse properties of fiber, matrix and composite*

	Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
UHMW-PE tape	2.0	14
epoxy	3.4	80
untreated HP-PE/epoxy	2.6	2.5
plasma HP-PE/epoxy	2.7	8

Scanning electron micrographs of transverse fracture surfaces show for untreated HP-PE composites fiber/matrix debonding (Figure 3a), whereas for specimens consisting of surface treated fibers, fiber fibrillation is observed (Figure 3b), indicating fiber dominated properties.

To obtain more quantitative information about the role of fiber anisotropy on the strength of HP-PE composites, a micromechanical analysis was performed to predict ultimate composite properties, based on its constituents. From the strength data of Table 1 it can already be concluded that in the case of perfect adhesion and assuming a simple 'strength-of-materials' series model, transverse composite strength is limited by the transverse fiber strength, since this value of approximately 14 MPa is significantly lower than that of the matrix.

Figure 3a. Scanning electron micrograph of transverse fracture surface of untreated HP-PE/epoxy composites showing debonding.

Figure 3b. Scanning electron micrograph of transverse fracture surface of plasma treated HP-PE/epoxy composites showing fiber fibrillation.

Upon transverse loading, a complex state of stress is induced in a composite as a result of differences in fiber and matrix properties. To account for stress concentrations on transverse composite strength a micromechanical analysis using finite element method was applied.

Adams and Doner [10] investigated the transverse response of a unidirectional composite using a finite difference method. Linear elastic plain strain analysis of a square array of elastic fibers in an elastic matrix was performed. Transverse stiffness and local states of stress were calculated for various constituent stiffness ratios E_t/E_m (with $E_t > E_m$) including the effect of fiber volume fraction i.e. fiber spacing. A similar approach using finite element analysis was adopted by Foye [11]. In both cases perfect fiber/matrix adhesion was assumed.

In the present study, preliminary results using plain stress finite element analysis are presented for a composite system with fibers of lower stiffness than that of the matrix. A hexagonal array of elastic fibers in an elastic matrix, assuming a perfect fiber-matrix interface bond was modelled. Similar to the analysis of Adams/Doner and Foye, local states of stress are calculated for various constituent stiffness ratios and fiber volume fractions. A section of a hexagonal array of a number of fibers in a matrix was modelled using the MENDAT linear elastic finite element analysis program.

Figure 4. Finite element mesh for hexagonal array.

Figure 4 shows the mesh used in this analysis. The composite body is assumed to be loaded by a normal stress. Interesting to note is that in the case of $E_t < E_m$, the highest values for the principal stress occur at the equator of the fiber, 90° from the transverse loading axis, whereas in the case of $E_t > E_m$ the highest stress concentration occurs at the top of the fiber.

Figure 5. Maximum stress concentration in fiber versus constituent stiffness ratio.

Figure 5 shows values of maximum principle stress as calculated for various E_m/E_f ratios and fiber volume fractions. For a typical HP-PE/epoxy composite this ratio will be approximately 1.6 (see Table 1), resulting in a stress concentration factor of 1.2 - 1.3 depending on the volume fraction.

Taking these stress concentrations into account, as calculated via finite element analysis, and following a 'strength-of-materials' approach where the composite strength is limited by either the matrix or the fiber strength magnified by a stress concentration factor [12], the transverse strength in the case of HP-PE/epoxy composites assuming perfect adhesion is given by:

$$\sigma_{2c} = \sigma_{2f} / SCF \quad (1)$$

Where σ_{2f} is the transverse fiber strength and SCF is the maximum stress concentration factor in the fiber as obtained from the finite element analysis.

Theoretical values for ultimate composite strength of approximately 10 - 11 MPa as calculated by Eq. 1 are in reasonable agreement with experimental data for surface treated HP-PE/epoxy composites (8 MPa).

The authors hasten to add that the micromechanical approach for predicting the transverse composite strength with respect to the failure criteria is oversimplified.

However it does provide a good insight in the effect of fiber anisotropy on composite strength. More sophisticated micromechanical analysis, including thermal induced residual stresses, crack propagation and interface failure as well as the effect of flaws or voids should result in more accurate predictions of the transversal strength.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A study has been carried out to obtain more insight in the role of adhesion and fiber anisotropy on the failure modes and strength of HP-PE fiber reinforced composites. SEM studies indicated with increasing levels of adhesion a change in failure mode from debonding to fiber splitting under shear and transverse loading conditions. Consequently properties of surface treated HP-PE/epoxy composites are fiber dominated rather than interface dominated.

Theoretical values for the transverse tensile strength, as obtained via a micromechanical approach assuming perfect adhesion, also indicate that the transverse strength is strongly dominated by the poor off-axis strength of the HP-PE fiber. Input fiber data for finite element micromechanical analysis were obtained from transverse testing of ultradrawn UHMW-PE tape.

5. REFERENCES

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